

Venture Capital Investments in Artificial Intelligence

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Description of the variables

deal_raised_amount	raised amount in USD (in log) in the focal round
d_venture_AI	dummy equal to 1 if the investee venture is in the AI domain, 0 otherwise
venture_age	venture age in the investment year
d_venture_late_stage	dummy equal to 1 if the invested venture is in the growth or late stage at the time of the investment (i.e. received the financing at least three years after its foundation), 0 otherwise
BVC_lead	dummy equal to 1 if the lead investor is a BVC, 0 otherwise
CVC_lead	dummy equal to 1 if the lead investor is a CVC, 0 otherwise
GVC_lead	dummy equal to 1 if the lead investor is a GVC, 0 otherwise
Other_VC_lead	dummy equal to 1 if the lead investor is other VC type, 0 otherwise
VC_age	(average) age of the lead investor(s) at investment year
VC_count	Natural logarithm of the number of VC investors coinvesting in the venture in the focal VC round.
VC_exp_IPO	VC experience (IPO), i.e. (max) cumulated number of successful exit (IPO or M&A) done by ventures backed by lead VC(s) up to investment year-1
VC_exp	VC experience (n. investments), i.e. (max) cumulated number of investments done by lead VC(s) (in log in the models) up to investment year-1
VC_AI_exp	VC experience in AI, i.e. (max) cumulated number of investments in AI ventures done by lead VC(s) up to investment year-1
VC_AI_exp_perc	VC experience in AI as percentage of cumulated number of investments in AI ventures done by lead VC(s) up to investment year-1 over total investments
d_high_VC_AI_exp	dummy equal to 1 if the percentage of AI investments on total investments done by lead VC(s) up to the year before the focal investment year is higher than the median of the variable distribution in the sample, 0 otherwise
country_gdppercapita	GDP per capita at the investment year of the country in which the venture is located
country_gdpgrowth	GDP growth at the investment year of the country in which the venture is located
d_AI_development	dummy equal to 1 if the number of AI patents filed in the year before the investment in the venture's country is higher than the median of the variable distribution in the sample, or if the percentage of funding amount in AI ventures over the total funding amount in the year before the investment in the venture's country is higher than the median of the variable distribution in the sample; 0 otherwise
d_AI_development_high	dummy equal to 1 if the number of AI patents filed in the year before the investment in the venture's country is higher than the third quartile of the variable distribution in the

venture_size	sample, or if the percentage of funding amount in AI ventures over the total funding amount in the year before the investment in the venture's country is higher than the third quartile of the variable distribution in the sample; 0 otherwise total assets of the invested venture in the year before the focal investment year, or in the year of the focal investment year for ventures founded in the same year in which they received their first VC round
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